

Zybert Cosmology Definitions

These definition can also be found at <https://www.qeios.com>

Zybert Cosmology (ZC)

A Cosmology conceived by Herr Dr Josef Zybert between 2018 and 2021 to explain and describe the evolution of the universe.

Zybert Cosmology introduces a new entity which comprises the universe - the Zybertsphere, denoted \textcircled{Z} . The inherent nature of Zybertspheres resolves baryonic asymmetry and accelerated expansion and explains the origin of voids and supermassive entities, UHECR's and background microwaves and more.

Within Zybertspheres, components of the acceleration caused by the central antineutron (or neutron) core and enveloping neutron (or antineutron) cloud of the Zybertspheres, known as the Action of Zybert $\Lambda\textcircled{Z}$ (which is the sum of $\Lambda\textcircled{Z}.\text{cosmic}$ and $\Lambda\textcircled{Z}.\text{local}$) create many observed Zybertspheric effects such as the precession of all orbits including planetary orbits such as of Mercury, the constant rotational velocity of galaxies, the increasing angular size of galaxies, velocity gains by spacecraft during planetary flybys and the bending of light and more.

Zybert Light is dynamic and any changes in the relative speed of light must be accounted for, as in GPS correction of the atomic clock L-band frequency in GPS satellites, because, the earth speeds up EMR from the GPS satellites in orbit down to the receivers on earth. In Zybert Cosmology this and other effects can be analysed using Classical Physics.

Zybert Cosmology redefines light as Zybert Light and gravity as Zybert Gravity and states that Zybert Time is fully concordant with Newtonian Mechanics and Quantum Mechanics.

In Zybert Cosmology 'the observable universe' is called 'our visible sphere'.

Our visible sphere is a miniscule insignificant little speck in our Zybertsphere, the Zybert Zybertsphere and Zybert Cosmology simulates the full life history of our, and any, Zybertsphere from birth to eternity.

Zybert Cosmology resolves the serious 5σ Hubble Crisis and most other of the 40+ anomalies which have been identified in Cosmology in recent decades.

The Zybert Cosmology Postulates

- 1 matter-antimatter repel
- 2 variable mass creation
- 3 instantaneous action of gravity
- 4 antigravity is coupled to antimatter as gravity is to matter
- 5 all motion is absolute relative to fixed space
- 6 the speed of light is additive with the source
- 7 light has an Eigen speed c , a Zybert speed \textcircled{C} (the absolute speed) and a relative speed \hat{c}
- 8 gravity is coupled to mass and light equally
- 9 for each neutron-antineutron pair $\Sigma E=0$ and therefore for each \textcircled{Z} $\Sigma E=0$ (speculatively)

Zybert Universe

The universe as conceived, described, analysed and simulated in Zybert Cosmology. Zybert Cosmology gives no hints of how big the universe is, or how old, or how it came to be. Nor whether mass and light appeared as, or after, empty space appeared. The fundamental cosmic entity in a Zybert Universe is the Zybertsphere \textcircled{Z} . It is likely that countless \textcircled{Z} 's were created before ours and countless after, and that the creation of \textcircled{Z} 's has been, is, and will continue to be, continually initiated throughout the universe. One solitary \textcircled{Z} would seem to be a waste of space. Hence a Zybert Universe has Zybertspheres much like the observable universe has galaxies and as galaxies have stars. The observable universe in Zybert Cosmology is referred to as our visible sphere.

Zybertsphere (\textcircled{Z})

The fundamental cosmic entity comprising the universe as defined in Zybert Cosmology, having a central spherical antineutron core enveloped by a spherical baryon cloud, or vice versa.

Related terms: Zybertspheric

$\textcircled{Z}0$	the centre of any Zybertsphere
$Z\textcircled{Z}$	our Zybertsphere the Zybert Zybertsphere
$Z\textcircled{Z}0$	the centre of our Zybertsphere

Zybert Mass ($\textcircled{Z}M$)

The mass of the central core or enveloping cloud of any \textcircled{Z} . Where the core is antineutrons then its mass is $\textcircled{Z}M^-$ and the enveloping cloud $\textcircled{Z}M^+$ and vice versa if the core is neutrons. The + indicates neutrons and - indicates antineutrons. Neutrons and antineutrons repel.

Zybert Mass Equation

The equation for the mass-time profile of mass increase in any \textcircled{Z}

$$M = Z_m * \text{Tanh} [T / Z_a - 1] + M_i$$

M is the log of $\textcircled{Z}M$

T is the log of $\textcircled{Z}T$

Z_m defines the final $\textcircled{Z}M$ of the Zybertsphere

Z_a influences the age and rate of expansion of the Zybertsphere

M_i is the initial mass and is usually taken as a neutron

Mathematically Z_m and Z_a set the inflexion point

Zybert Acceleration ($\textcircled{Z}A$)

Acceleration at any point in a Zybertsphere caused by the central core (of antineutrons or neutrons) and the enveloping cloud (of neutrons or antineutrons). The all-pervasive influence in \textcircled{Z} 's is $\textcircled{Z}A$.

$\Delta\textcircled{Z}A$	$\textcircled{Z}A.2 - \textcircled{Z}A.1$	the relative acceleration between any two points in a \textcircled{Z}
$\textcircled{Z}A'$	$\delta\textcircled{Z}A/\delta\textcircled{Z}R$	gradient of $\textcircled{Z}A$ at any point in a \textcircled{Z}
$\textcircled{Z}A^+$		$\textcircled{Z}A$ due to a neutron core or cloud
$\textcircled{Z}A^-$		$\textcircled{Z}A$ due to an antineutron core or cloud

Axis of Zybert (F(Z))

The fundamental axis in all (Z)'s is the Axis of Zybert which is between the (Z) centre and an observer or entity such as earth. The Axis of Zybert is of great importance because many Zybertspheric effects are caused by the Action of Zybert $\Lambda(Z)$ of which the cosmic component is a component of Zybert Acceleration (ZA) which is referenced to the Axis of Zybert F(Z).

Angle of Zybert ($\theta(Z)$)

Any angle to the Axis of Zybert F(Z). The Angle of Zybert is essential for determining the cosmic Action of Zybert $\Lambda(Z)$.cosmic. The Angle of Zybert is the primary and fundamental angle in Zybertspheres because it is the angle with respect to the Axis of Zybert and it is the position along the Axis of Zybert which determines (ZA) and (ZA)'.

Zybert Gravity (ZA)

Zybert Gravity acts instantaneously.
Matter-matter and antimatter-antimatter attract. Matter-antimatter repel.
Antigravity is coupled to antimatter just as gravity is coupled to matter.
Zybert Gravity is coupled to mass and light equally, each is accelerated by and accelerates by GM/R^2 .

Action of Zybert ($\Lambda(Z)$)

The component of Zybert Acceleration (ZA) and local A causing Zybertspheric effects.
It is $\Lambda(Z)$ which causes Zybertspheric effects such as the precession of all orbits including planetary orbits such as of Mercury, the constant rotational velocity of galaxies, the increasing angular size of galaxies, velocity gains by spacecraft during planetary flybys, the local and cosmic components of the bending of light and GPS inaccuracy and more.

$\Lambda(Z).c$ $\Lambda(Z).cosmic$ Action of Zybert which acts over cosmic distances

$\Lambda(Z).l$ $\Lambda(Z).local$ Action of Zybert which acts over local distances

$\Lambda(Z)'$ $\delta\Lambda(Z)/\delta(Z)R$ gradient of the Action of Zybert

Both $\Lambda(Z).c$ and $\Lambda(Z).l$ act everywhere within a Zybertsphere but $\Lambda(Z).l \gg \Lambda(Z).c$ locally and dominates whereas over cosmic distances $\Lambda(Z).l \ll \Lambda(Z).c$ and $\Lambda(Z).c$ dominates and the dominance is usually a gradual transition from one to the other as for example with the constant rotational velocity of galaxies. But generally when analysing local effects $\Lambda(Z) \approx \Lambda(Z).local$ can be assumed and when analysing cosmic effects $\Lambda(Z) \approx \Lambda(Z).cosmic$ can be assumed, but both need to be considered for a full analysis.

$\Lambda(Z).cosmic = \Delta(Z)A * \cos(\theta(Z))$ and mostly interest is between two entities within (ZA).

$\Lambda(Z).local = \Delta A * \cos(\theta)$ and mostly the interest is between an entity and the centre of the local mass but becomes important for an interaction between say two satellites in earths' gravitational field.

Zybert Velocity (ZV)

The velocity of mass or light in Zybertspheres. Velocity in Zybertspheres is absolute, relative to both fixed space and (Z) centres which are fixed in fixed space. The Zybertspheric velocity of mass is denoted (ZV) but light is specially denoted (C) the Zybert speed of light (the absolute speed).

Zybert Light

In Zybert Cosmology space is a fixed background.

Zybert Light has an Eigen Speed c , currently defined as 299792458m/s.

Zybert Light has a Relative Speed \hat{c} , as measured by an observer, and \hat{c} can be $<$ or $=$ or $>$ c or 0.

Zybert Light has a Zybert Speed \textcircled{c} , an absolute speed relative to both fixed space and Zybertsphere centres which are fixed in fixed space.

The Eigen Speed is additive with the speed of the source giving its Zybert Speed \textcircled{c} .

The Zybert Speed is further changed locally by any M , M^+ or M^- through an acceleration GM/R^2 , and, cosmically by $\textcircled{z}M$, $\textcircled{z}M^-$ or $\textcircled{z}M^+$ through an acceleration $G\textcircled{z}M/\textcircled{z}R^2$ for the core and $(\textcircled{z}R/\textcircled{z}Ro)G\textcircled{z}M/\textcircled{z}Ro^2$ for the cloud.

In the lab $\hat{c} \approx c$ but usually $\hat{c} \neq c$, mainly because there is always a $\Lambda\textcircled{z}$, no matter how small.

Zybert Effect

The term used to differentiate between the Doppler Effect.

Doppler Effect a change in the wavelength of sound in a medium

Zybert Effect a change in the speed of light in a vacuum

Zybertshift (\textcircled{z})

The ratio of the observed speed of light to the Eigen Speed of light. Zybertshift.local, as uberZybertshift.earth, is an increase in the velocity of EMR from say GPS satellites to receivers on earth, and with GPS the frequency of EMR from the satellites must be corrected to offset this increase in EMR speed.

\textcircled{z}	Zybertshift	\hat{c}/c or $v.\text{observed}/v.\text{emitted}$ etc
\textcircled{u}	unterZybertshift	The relative speed of light $\hat{c} < c$
\textcircled{u}	uberZybertshift	The relative speed of light $\hat{c} > c$
$\textcircled{z}.\text{local}$	Zybertshift.local	Zybertshift caused by a local M , M^+ or M^- , which creates a $\Lambda\textcircled{z}.\text{local}$
$\textcircled{z}.\text{cosmic}$	Zybertshift.cosmic	Zybertshift caused by a cosmic $\textcircled{z}M$, $\textcircled{z}M^+$ and $\textcircled{z}M^-$, which creates a $\Lambda\textcircled{z}.\text{cosmic}$
$\textcircled{z}.\text{sun}$	Zybertshift.sun	Zybertshift caused by our Sun
\textcircled{u}	unterZybertshift.sun	light travelling away from the sun has $\hat{c} < c$
$\textcircled{z}.\text{earth}$	Zybertshift.earth	Zybertshift caused by the earth
\textcircled{u}	uberZybertshift.earth	light travelling toward earth has $\hat{c} > c$

Zybertrefraction ($\mathbb{Z}\theta$)

Zybertshift is a change in light speed and Zybertrefraction is a change in light direction, given as $\mathbb{Z}\theta$, and which has a related geometric Zybertrefraction $\mathbb{Z}\theta.g$.

$\mathbb{Z}\theta$	$\delta y/\delta x$	the instantaneous angle of the light path at any point B in the light path relative to the angle at point A
$\mathbb{Z}\theta.g$	$\Delta y/\Delta x$	the geometric angle between points A and B in a light path

Generally $\Delta y/\Delta x < \delta y/\delta x$ due to the nature of the curvature of motion in \mathbb{Z} 's.

It is $\delta y/\delta x$ which is observed as $\mathbb{Z}\theta$. $\Delta y/\Delta x$ represents the geometry of the source and observer.

$\mathbb{Z}\theta$ causes some $\mathbb{Z}z$. Both $\mathbb{Z}z$ and $\mathbb{Z}\theta$ are reflected in vector \mathbb{C} .

$\mathbb{Z}\theta.local$	Zybertrefraction.local	Zybertrefraction caused by a local mass M^+ or M^- through the Action of Zybert $\Lambda(\mathbb{Z}.local)$
$\mathbb{Z}\theta.sun$	Zybertrefraction.sun	local Zybertrefraction by the sun
$\mathbb{Z}\theta.cosmic$	Zybertrefraction.cosmic	Zybertrefraction caused by $\mathbb{Z}M$ through the Action of Zybert $\Lambda(\mathbb{Z}.cosmic)$
$\mathbb{Z}\theta.Hyades$	Zybertrefraction.Hyades	cosmic Zybertrefraction of light from Hyades caused by $\Lambda(\mathbb{Z}.cosmic)$ to the sun and $\Lambda(\mathbb{Z}.local)$ by the sun

An important consequence of Zybertrefraction, specifically that $\delta y/\delta x \neq \Delta y/\Delta x$ i.e. the observed angle is not the geometric angle, is that cosmic objects are not where they appear to be. For example, in an analysis of light from Hyades photographed by Eddington in Jan & May 1919, Hyades, if centred at $y=0$ and projecting $\delta y/\delta x$ of the reference light rays of Jan 1919 gives its apparent position as $y=-4.65614E17m$ and the deflected light rays during the eclipse of May 1919, as $y=-4.65608E17m$. In ZC the 'non-deflected reference light rays' do not indicate the true position of the source.

Zybert Expansion ($\mathbb{Z}X$)

Expansion of the enveloping cloud of Zybertspheres accelerated outward by the central core.

$\mathbb{Z}X$	Absolute Zybert Expansion	Zybert velocity of mass outward from the \mathbb{Z} centre.
$\Delta\mathbb{Z}X = \mathbb{Z}X.2 - \mathbb{Z}X.1$	Relative Zybert Expansion	Difference between the Absolute Zybert Expansion of an entity at two different times.
$\mathbb{Z}Z = \Delta\mathbb{Z}X/\Delta\mathbb{Z}R$	Normalised Relative Zybert Expansion	The Relative Zybert Expansion of an entity divided by the distance travelled during the time of the Relative Zybert Expansion.

Zybert Parameter ($\mathbb{Z}Z$)

A fundamental parameter in Zybert Cosmology which is equivalent to Normalized Relative Zybert Expansion.

$\mathbb{Z}Z = \Delta\mathbb{Z}X/\Delta\mathbb{Z}R$	Zybert Parameter or Normalised Relative Zybert Expansion
$\mathbb{Z}\dot{Z} = \delta\mathbb{Z}Z/\delta\mathbb{Z}T$	Time derivative of the Zybert Parameter

The Zybert Parameter $\mathbb{Z}Z$ is the counterpart to the Hubble Constant H_0 .

But whereas H_0 represents the age of the observable universe $\mathbb{Z}Z$ does not.

Also, $\mathbb{Z}Z$ is the relative velocity of an entity relative to itself at a different time but H_0 is the relative velocity between an entity and earth.

Zybert Time ($\text{\textcircled{Z}}T$)

Zybert Time is fully concordant with Newtonian Mechanics and Quantum Mechanics.

Zybert Density ($\text{\textcircled{Z}}\rho$)

The Density at any point in a Zybertsphere. Zybert Density is generally similar on any spherical shell at $\text{\textcircled{Z}}R$. Zybert Density is higher near the central core and 0 at the edge of the Zybertsphere. At some $\text{\textcircled{Z}}R$ in our $\text{\textcircled{Z}}$ $\text{\textcircled{Z}}\rho$ is the same as our visible sphere (in Zybert Cosmology the observable universe is known as 'our visible sphere').

Zybertzone ($\text{\textcircled{Z}}zz$)

A diffuse spherical annulus in the baryon (or antibaryon) cloud of Zybertspheres where conditions are conducive to star formation. From the Zybertzone, densities increase toward the central core and decrease toward the Zybertsphere outer surface.

Our visible sphere (in Zybert Cosmology the observable universe is called our visible sphere) is in the Zybertzone of our Zybertsphere, $\text{\textcircled{Z}}zz$, where the density is around $1E-26\text{kg/m}^3$.

Zybertwind

In the turbulent creation zone at the matter-antimatter interface, newly created neutrons decay and combine and re-combine into protons, electrons, light nuclei, photons etc. along with some anti-equivalents from entrapped antineutrons which decay into antiprotons/antielectrons or combine with neutrons as photons and all are repelled by the central core and stream out from the neutron-antineutron creation zone to form Zybertwind.

Zybertwind plasma interacts with Zybertzone plasma and emits Blackbody Bremsstrahlung microwaves known as Zybert Microwave Radiation ZMR.

Zybert Microwave Radiation (ZMR)

The Blackbody radiation created when Zybertwind plasma interacts with Zybertzone plasma. This occurs throughout the Zybertzone and therefore throughout our visible sphere.

ZMR manifestly correlates with the cosmic distribution of mass.

ZMR creates the ZME (Zybert Microwave Environment).

Zybert Microwave Environment (ZME)

All the superimposed unterZybertshifted individual ZMR in all directions is all sky microwave EMR – the Zybert Microwave Environment ZME, and manifestly correlates with the cosmic distribution of mass.

290Ghz ZMR at $2E3\text{Mpc}$ ($\text{\textcircled{Z}}z=0.55$) or ZME within $4E3\text{Mpc}$, if using sensors of $> 30\text{Ghz}$, is measured as Blackbody EMR peaking at 160Ghz, equivalent to a Blackbody at 2.725K, but, ZME is unrelated to a cosmic temperature.

Inverse Compton Scattering between, Zybertwind and Zybertzone plasmas, increases downwind velocity of photons, which distorts Zybertshift of light, creating a dipole in the ZME.

In Zybert Cosmology ESA-Planck is not measuring primordial photons but is measuring local ZME of recent ZMR. In ZC this resolves the 5σ Hubble Crisis declared in 2020.

Neutron Spheres (NS)

Spheres comprising neutrons formed either early in the evolution of our (M^+) Zybetsphere by local gravity consolidating clusters of neutrons which formed randomly in the dense neutron cloud near the central core early in its evolution, to form Galactic Neutron Spheres (GNS), or, are the remnants of dead stars after the stars have spent their fuel, to form Stellar Neutron Spheres (SNS). In M^- Zybetspheres these would be Antineutron Spheres.

Galactic Neutron Spheres (GNS)

Neutron Spheres at the centre of galaxies. NS's are formed early in the evolution of Zybetspheres in the dense neutron cloud near the central core from random neutron clusters which had formed earlier, before neutrons transformed into protons/electrons, and then coalesced under local gravity. NS's can merge with other NS's and are added to by newer neutrons streaming out being repelled from the central core. In our Zybetsphere with an antineutron core GNS's are neutrons, but, in Zybetspheres with a central neutron core GNS's would be antineutrons. The mass of GNS's can be less than SNS's but can range up to billions of SNS's.

Stellar Neutron Spheres (SNS)

Neutron spheres which remain after a star has spent its fuel. In our Zybetsphere with an antineutron core SNS's are neutrons, but, in Zybetspheres with a central neutron core, SNS's would be antineutrons.

Zybert TGM

This is the method in Zybert Cosmology for calculating Total Galactic Mass (TGM) of galaxies. It uses measured V vs R data (by measuring the \textcircled{z} of light from the centre of the galaxy outward). The Method reflects an aspect of Zybetspheres where only one $\Lambda(\textcircled{z})'$ (local and cosmic) with only one M vs R profile can reproduce the measured V vs R curve for each galaxy, calculated using $V^2/R = \Lambda(\textcircled{z}).\text{local} + \Lambda(\textcircled{z}).\text{cosmic} \cdot R$.

Zybert Golden Correlations

Many Zybetsphere parameters have linear log-log correlations to $R^2 = 1$ or ≈ 1 . These correlations occur during the evolution of individual Zybetspheres and also for multiple Zybetspheres at $\textcircled{z} = 7E4$ in their evolution, equivalent to our present day. The utility of Zybert Golden Correlations is that interpolations and extrapolations are simple and accurate. But they also show that the highly complex physical Zybetspheres can have a simple and elegant mathematical representation using a few well known and trusted equations within Zybert Cosmology which is based on a few bold postulates.

Zybetsphere Coordinate System (ZCS)

The coordinate system for Zybetspheres where the primary axis, the z -axis, is the ultimate fundamental axis in Zybetspheres the Axis of Zybert $H(\textcircled{z})$. The ZCS simplifies the geometry since many \textcircled{z} effects are caused by $\Lambda(\textcircled{z}).\text{cosmic}$ which is referenced to $H(\textcircled{z})$ through $\theta(\textcircled{z})$. The Axis of Zybert is also directly related to the inhomogeneity and anisotropy of Zybetspheres.

The Zybert Process (TZP)

The unknown process which creates neutron-antineutron pairs which evolve into Zybertspheres. The rate of pair creation is represented by the Zybert Mass Equation. Speculatively, TZP creates neutron-antineutron pairs where $\Sigma E=0$, and therefore for each $\textcircled{Z} \Sigma E=0$.

Our visible sphere

The Zybert Cosmology equivalent of 'the observable universe'.

Our visible sphere is within our Zybertsphere $Z\textcircled{Z}$, somewhere in the Zybertzone $Z\textcircled{Z}zz$ - a stelliferous spherical annulus within the baryon cloud surrounding the antineutron core of our Zybertsphere. Our visible-sphere is some 93 billion light years across. Every observer in a Zybertsphere has their own visible sphere. Observers near the inner and outer surfaces of the Zybertzone will observe a patch of their visible sphere in one or other direction along the Axis of Zybert which is different to all the other directions.